

CELISE project: how to help SMEs and rural areas using the bioeconomy

Alberto Coz¹, Laura Andze², R. Fernando Colmenares-Quintero³, Grzegorz Kowaluk⁴, Josefa Fernández-Ferreras¹, Tamara Llano¹

¹ Chemistry and Process & Resources Engineering Department. University of Cantabria, Santander, Spain

² Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry, Riga, Latvia

³ Engineering Research Institute, Universidad Cooperativa de Colombia, Medellín, Colombia

⁴ Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Warsaw, Poland

E-mail contact: alberto.coz@unican.es

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Abstract

A rural area is an open swath of land that has few homes or other buildings, and not very many people [1]. Many rural areas in Europe and Latin America are experiencing a long-term reduction in their population. In Europe, according to a new report of Eurostat [2] particularly those of a working age and young people (under 20). This trend has serious consequences for both urban and rural areas through the exacerbation of socioeconomic disparities across regions [3].

In order to solve the depopulation problems and to increase the business models in rural areas within the bioeconomy, a new MSCA-RISE project from H2020, CELISE project (<https://celise.unican.es/>), is being developed. The main objective of the project is the transfer of knowledge about sustainable cellulose-based materials from biomass residues which can be used not only in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), but also in rural and vulnerable areas of Europe and Latin America.

The CELISE project is based on all of the sustainability issues: (i) environmental- due to the use of natural additives, residues of biomass, and the production of bioenergy; (ii) economic- with new business models of construction, packaging and health products as well as every-day and artisan goods; and (iii) social- studying rural and vulnerable areas in Colombia (post-conflict) and Ecuador, using portable and adaptable equipment, and taking into account gender equality and educational programmes.

The project is divided into five work packages (biomass processing, social business model tools, transfer of knowledge of the action, exploitation, communication and public engagement, and coordination and management of the action) with the participation of 25 partners, 12 academic institutions from Europe, 8 SMEs from Europe, and 5 institutions from Latin America. The budget is used for planned secondments for 42 participants (135 person/months), 45% being women, and 40% early-stage researchers.

The most important results of the project will be used for: (i) strengthening cooperation in research and innovation through the mobility of participants, the training of young researchers and lifelong learning opportunities; (ii) connecting with the reality of vulnerable areas and gender inequality; (iii) increasing the relationship with the concept of biorefinery in different local areas; (iv) reinforcing the economic development by the innovation of adhesives and additives and other recovery alternatives that are obtained from cellulosic biomass residues in relation to the bioeconomy; and (v) carrying out a communication strategy throughout the entire life of the project.

References

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[3] European Union, 2023. Taking action to tackle rural depopulation. https://rural-vision.europa.eu/events/taking-action-tackle-rural-depopulation-2023-06-29_en. Accessed 14 02 2024.

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